

Influence of Arc Voltage and Travel Speed on the Environmental Footprint of WAAM: An Experimental LCA Approach

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a cradle-to-gate Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) process using the gas metal arc welding (GMAW) method for ER70S-6 steel deposition. Two deposition strategies, high-voltage high-speed (HVHS) and low-voltage low-speed (LVLS), were experimentally implemented to explore the environmental implications of adjusting the arc voltage and travel speed. Experimental measurements of electrical energy consumption were obtained using a JAM-300 power analyzer, while wall geometry (height and minimum width) was evaluated through ImageJ analysis to define the functional unit of a 15-layer wall. The environmental modeling was performed in SimaPro using the Ecoinvent v3 database and the EPD2018 impact method, complemented by endpoint aggregation through the ReCiPe 2016 (Hierarchist) approach. The results reveal that increasing the arc voltage while reducing the deposition time marginally elevates total environmental burdens. The global warming potential (GWP) of the HVHS strategy (0.746 kg CO₂-eq) was only 0.94% higher than LVLS (0.739 kg CO₂-eq), while total endpoint impacts were approximately 10.6% greater for HVHS. This increase is attributed to the higher instantaneous power demand, which outweighs the shorter process duration. Overall, process optimization in WAAM must balance energy efficiency with productivity, as increasing voltage does not necessarily reduce environmental impact. The findings provide valuable insights into the influence of electrical parameters on the sustainability of WAAM.

Keywords: Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing, Life Cycle Assessment, Environmental Impact, Energy Consumption, Arc Voltage, Travel Speed, GMAW, Sustainability, ReCiPe 2016, Ecoinvent

WAAM	wire arc additive manufacturing	MAG	Metal Active Gas
AM	additive manufacturing	MIG	Metal inert Gas
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment	GMAW	gas-metal arc welding
GWP	global warming potential	LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
AP	acidification potential	LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
EP	eutrophication potential	ODP	Ozone layer depletion potential
POP	photochemical oxidation potential	HVHS	high voltage – high speed
LVLS	low voltage – low speed		

1. INTRODUCTION

Human activities over the past century, especially fossil fuel combustion, land use change, industrialization, and large-scale manufacturing, have substantially increased atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gases, foremost among them carbon dioxide (CO₂) [1]. This enhanced greenhouse effect has driven a global rise in average temperatures, melting of ice caps, sea level rise, changes in precipitation patterns, and more frequent extreme weather events. The scientific consensus is clear: limiting global warming to acceptable levels demands deep reductions in CO₂ emissions across all sectors, including manufacturing and

metal production. In that context, identifying industrial processes that can reduce the carbon footprint or shift emissions upstream is an essential strategy for sustainable development [2].

In this context, the concept of sustainable manufacturing has gained increasing traction. Sustainable manufacturing aims to reconcile economic performance and productivity with environmental stewardship by minimizing resource consumption, waste, and emissions across the full life cycle. Within the realm of metal production and fabrication, additive manufacturing (AM), in particular WAAM, has emerged as a promising approach because of its potential to reduce raw material waste, improve material utilization (i.e. lower buy-to-fly ratios), and shorten supply chains for large components [3, 4].

Nonetheless, to credibly establish the environmental advantages of WAAM, a LCA framework is indispensable. Through LCA, one can quantify cradle-to-gate (or cradle-to-end-of-life) emissions, including those from raw material production, energy consumption in deposition and post-processing, tool and consumable usage, and waste management [5]. In welding and arc-based processes, changes in voltage alter arc stability, heat input, wire melting efficiency, transfer modes (e.g., pulsed, dip, spray), and thus the specific energy consumption per unit deposited material. Conversely, suboptimal voltage settings might degrade deposition efficiency, increase defects or rework, and inflate environmental burdens [6]. An LCA framework holds promise because slight adjustments in arc voltage may cascade through multiple stages: reduced energy input per gram of deposit, lower heat waste, possibly less post-machining, and hence lower embodied CO₂ [7].

Recent LCA studies on WAAM have begun to clarify its potential. For example, Shah et al. [8] evaluate the environmental life cycle of WAAM parts and highlight that assumptions about power consumption, idle times, and post-processing strongly influence CO₂ outcomes. Spreafico et al. [9] explore prospective LCA projections for future WAAM systems to reveal that even moderate improvements in energy efficiency or deposition rates can shift net environmental performance significantly. Reis et al. [10] compare WAAM and CNC milling for different geometries and report that WAAM offers material savings of 40-70% and reduces environmental impacts by 12-47% relative to subtractive methods; they also show that the shielding gas is a non-negligible inventory item. Henckell et al. [11] demonstrated that optimizing arc voltage and current in GMAW-based WAAM can reduce specific energy input by up to 25%, improving deposition efficiency and lowering potential carbon emissions. Bekker and Verlinden [12] conducted a cradle-to-gate LCA of stainless-steel WAAM parts, finding that electricity demand ($\approx 2.7 \text{ kW kg}^{-1}$) dominates environmental impacts; excessive voltage or heat input significantly raises CO₂-eq emissions.

Despite growing attention to sustainability in metal additive manufacturing, few studies have experimentally quantified how variations in electrical parameters affect the environmental performance of WAAM processes. Previous works have mainly estimated energy demand based on theoretical or machine-rated values, often neglecting real-time measurements and the combined influence of voltage and travel speed. In this study, we experimentally measured the actual energy consumption and geometric outputs of WAAM walls fabricated under different arc voltage and travel speed conditions. Two representative process strategies, HVHS and LVLS, were selected for cradle-to-gate LCA comparison. The environmental impacts were modeled in SimaPro using Ecoinvent datasets and evaluated through both midpoint (EPD2018) and endpoint (ReCiPe 2016) indicators. The main objectives were to (i) assess how voltage-speed combinations influence the total environmental footprint of WAAM, (ii) identify the trade-off between deposition rate and energy efficiency.

Method

To facilitate a systematic analysis, this section examines the WAAM process through two key aspects: its environmental impact and mechanical performance.

1.1 Mechanical

In this study, all specimens were fabricated using a fully automated three-axis CNC-controlled WAAM system equipped with a GMAW torch (ER70S-6 wire, 1.2 mm diameter) and a digital power source, which is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The WAAM experimental setup

The experiments were designed according to a full factorial matrix in which voltage and travel speed were varied at three levels each, as shown in Table 1. This set of experiments was conducted to determine the influential input parameters so that, based on the output characteristics, a subsequent performance function could be established. The deposited walls are shown in Figure 2.

Table 1. Experimental matrix for WAAM process parameter variation

Run	Voltage (V)	Travel Speed (mm/min)	Overall height (mm)	Min width (mm)
1	8	100	26.1	7.2
2	8	150	21.9	6.4
3	8.5	100	27.4	7.3
4	8	200	24.4	6.1
5	7.5	100	27.2	7.7
6	8	150	23.7	7.1
7	7.5	150	21.3	6
8	8	150	22.6	6.2
9	7.5	200	23.3	5.4
10	8.5	200	19.9	5.4
11	8.5	150	21.5	6

Fig. 2. The fabricated specimens for WAAM process parameter variation

Wire feed rate, shielding gas flow, interlayer cooling time, and other auxiliary parameters were kept constant to ensure that only the target variables affected the results, as depicted in Table 2. After deposition, the geometrical features such as overall height and minimum width of each build were measured using ImageJ software.

Table 2. WAAM input parameters

process	WAAM
Voltage (V)	7.5-8-8.5
Travel Speed (mm/min)	100-150-200
Wire Feed Rate (m/min)	3.5
Gas flow rate (L/min)	13
Inter-layer cooling time (s)	180
Electrode Diameter (mm)	1.2

The deposition process was implemented on an automated XYZ motion system controlling the torch movement and switching cycles. Identical toolpaths were executed under different gas environments through G-code programming and synchronized digital I/O control. A JAM 300 power analyzer measured the electrical demand of the setup, distinguishing between arc energy, auxiliary motion/cooling loads, and standby power.

1.2 Environmental

The LCA in this study was conducted in accordance with the ISO 14040/44 framework [13]. This standardized methodology comprises four iterative stages, as illustrated in Figure 3:

1-Goal and Scope Definition: The objectives of the study are established, and the functional unit and system boundaries are defined.

2-Life Cycle Inventory (LCI): Inputs of materials and energy, along with outputs of emissions and waste, are quantified. This phase combines foreground data from direct measurements with background processes from established databases.

3-Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA): The inventory data are translated into potential environmental impacts using characterization models; this study employs the ReCiPe 2016 methodology.

4-Interpretation: The results are critically evaluated to draw conclusions, explain limitations, and provide recommendations.

Fig. 3. 4 stages of LCA

1.2.1 Scope and goal

The goal of this investigation is to quantify and compare the environmental impacts of two distinct WAAM process strategies: HVHS and LVLS deposition (Trials 4 and 7 from Table 1. The functional unit is defined as

one deposited wall, 10 cm in length and consisting of 15 layers, achieving a similar height and minimum wall width. This ensures that both deposition strategies produce comparable final geometries for a fair assessment. The system boundary is cradle-to-gate, encompassing the upstream production of raw materials (wire manufacture and alloying), the manufacture and transport of consumables, and the measured on-machine electricity consumption for both deposition and any subsequent finishing operations. The use phase and end-of-life processing are excluded from this study.

1.2.2 LCI

In SimaPro, the process chain was modeled as a sequence of linked unit processes. The background datasets from Ecoinvent v3 were employed for all energy and material inputs [14]. The inventory for both the HVHS and LVLS scenarios is presented in Table 3. The model includes the upstream production of the ER70S-6 steel wire, encompassing the "Hot rolled" and "Drawn steel wire" stages [14]. The key differentiating input is the "GMAW welding electricity," which reflects the directly measured arc energy consumption for each parameter set. Auxiliary power for the "WAAM motion system" was also accounted for. All electricity use was modeled using Iran's regional medium-voltage grid mix [15]. As the shielding gas (CO₂) was constant across both scenarios, its impact is a background constant, allowing the analysis to isolate the effect of the electrical and kinematic parameters.

Table 3. LCI data for the WAAM process under different voltage conditions

Inventory	Process Source in Ecoinvent 3	Unit	HVHS	LVLS
			Value	Value
Hot rolled	Hot rolling, low-carbon steel	kg	0.31	0.31
Drawn steel wire	Wire drawing, low-carbon steel	kg	0.225	0.225
GMAW electricity	Electricity input for welding	kWh	0.37	0.27
WAAM Motion system	Electricity, medium voltage	kWh	0.01	0.01
Shielding gas	Carbon dioxide, liquid	kg	0.09	0.12

2. Results and discussion

A cradle-to-gate LCA was conducted to evaluate the environmental performance of the WAAM process under two distinct parameter sets: HVHS and LVLS. The life cycle inventory integrated foreground data, including wire consumption, energy for deposition, and auxiliary systems, with background processes from the Ecoinvent 3 database within the SimaPro 9.2 software.

The results were characterized using the EPD2018 impact assessment method. Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) provide a standardized, multi-category framework for comparing environmental impacts, making them highly suitable for contrasting alternative manufacturing routes [16, 17]. The EPD2018 method translates inventory data into a comprehensive set of impact categories, including GWP, Acidification Potential (AP), Eutrophication Potential (EP), Photochemical Oxidant Creation Potential (POCP), Abiotic Resource Depletion (elements and fossil), Water Scarcity, and Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP). This allows for a clear, category-by-category interpretation of how deposition strategy influences environmental burdens [18, 19, 20]. The resulting impact scores per functional unit are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Life Cycle Impact Assessment results for HVHS and LVLS WAAM strategies using the EPD2018 method

Impact category	Unit	WAAM - IR - HVHS	WAAM - IR - LVLS
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	0.7464582	0.73950341
Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	0.002179538	0.002117205
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ --- eq	0.000446774	0.000484607
Photochemical oxidation	kg NMVOC	0.001674496	0.001640359

Ozone layer depletion	kg CFC-11 eq	5.73E-08	5.42E-08
Water scarcity	m3 eq	0.44806297	0.49534572
Abiotic depletion, elements	kg Sb eq	1.52E-06	1.96E-06
Abiotic depletion, fossil fuels	MJ	7.7860167	7.4203119

Fig. 4. LCA results of the EPD 2018 impact category

GWP (reported in kg CO₂-eq) aggregates all greenhouse-gas emissions into a single carbon-equivalent metric, so it indicates the overall climate burden of the process [21]. For the two deposition strategies, GWP is 0.746458 kg CO₂-eq (HVHS) versus 0.739503 kg CO₂-eq (LVLS); HVHS is ≈0.94% higher than LVLS. The difference is very small and consistent with a trade-off between higher instantaneous arc power at elevated voltage and the reduced total arc-on time achieved by faster travel speeds: in this inventory, the slightly larger instantaneous power draw under HVHS appears to outweigh the time savings just enough to raise net CO₂-eq emissions per wall.

AP (reported in kg SO₂-eq) quantifies emissions (SO₂, NO_x, NH₃) that acidify soils and water bodies and is principally driven by combustion-related emissions from electricity generation and upstream material processes [22]. In this study, AP is 0.0021795 kg SO₂-eq (HVHS) versus 0.0021172 kg SO₂-eq (LVLS), HVHS is ≈2.9% higher than LVLS. The small increase under HVHS is consistent with a modest rise in instantaneous electrical demand at higher arc voltage: greater electricity use per unit time increases upstream NO_x and SO₂ emissions from the grid, which in turn raise the AP score [23].

EP (reported as kg PO₄³⁻-eq) captures nutrient releases (nitrogen and phosphorus species) that stimulate algal blooms and is influenced by agricultural inputs, wastewater discharges, and atmospheric N emissions

associated with energy production [24]. In this investigation, EP is 0.000446774 kg PO_4^{3-} -eq (HVHS) versus 0.000484607 kg PO_4^{3-} -eq (LVLS), HVHS is $\approx 7.8\%$ lower than LVLS. The reduction under HVHS likely reflects the net effect of shorter total deposition time and modestly lower cumulative auxiliary and material-handling demands (for example, reduced cooling or circulation runtime and potentially less wire/spatter loss), which lower the summed upstream releases that drive eutrophication; small changes in the electricity demand profile can also alter atmospheric N emissions from the grid and thus EP [25].

POCP quantifies the potential for volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and NO_x to form ground-level ozone and smog and is therefore sensitive to VOC/ NO_x precursor emissions from energy generation and industrial processes [26]. In this work, POCP is 0.0016745 kg NMVOC-eq (HVHS) versus 0.0016404 kg NMVOC-eq (LVLS), HVHS is $\approx 2.1\%$ higher than LVLS. The small increase for HVHS is consistent with a modest rise in instantaneous electrical demand at higher arc voltage: greater short-term power draw can elevate upstream NO_x and VOC emissions from the grid, which in turn raise photochemical-oxidation scores [27].

ODP (reported kg CFC-11-eq) is effectively negligible for metal-fabrication chains unless halogenated refrigerants or similar substances are involved upstream [28]. In this study, ODP is 5.73×10^{-8} kg CFC-11-eq (HVHS) versus 5.42×10^{-8} kg CFC-11-eq (LVLS), HVHS is $\approx 5.7\%$ higher than LVLS, but both values are trivial in absolute terms and unlikely to be environmentally significant. By contrast, abiotic-elemental depletion (kg Sb-eq) shows a meaningful difference: 1.52×10^{-6} kg Sb-eq (HVHS) versus 1.96×10^{-6} kg Sb-eq (LVLS), so HVHS is $\approx 22.5\%$ lower in elemental depletion. The ODP difference likely reflects minor upstream dataset variability rather than any process-level halogen chemistry, whereas the lower elemental depletion for HVHS plausibly arises from reduced cumulative material use or lower consumable/wire losses at higher travel speed (less upstream production and associated trace-metal burdens per functional unit) [29].

Water scarcity (m^3 -eq) quantifies freshwater consumption and competition for water resources across upstream processes [30]. In this study, water scarcity is 0.448063 m^3 -eq (HVHS) versus 0.495346 m^3 -eq (LVLS), HVHS is $\approx 9.6\%$ lower than LVLS (percentage relative to LVLS). The reduction for HVHS likely stems from shorter total deposition time and reduced auxiliary running hours (cooling, pumps, and other water-using systems), which lower cumulative industrial and thermoelectric water withdrawals attributed to the functional unit; small decreases in material handling and rework under faster travel speeds can also reduce upstream water demand tied to feedstock production and processing [31].

Abiotic resource depletion is reported as elemental depletion (kg Sb-eq) and fossil-fuel depletion (MJ). For the two parameter sets, the values are 1.52×10^{-6} kg Sb-eq (HVHS) vs 1.96×10^{-6} kg Sb-eq (LVLS), HVHS is $\approx 22.4\%$ lower in elemental depletion, and 7.7860 MJ (HVHS) vs 7.4203 MJ (LVLS) for fossil fuels, HVHS is $\approx 4.9\%$ higher in embodied non-renewable energy (percentages relative to the LVLS baseline). The lower elemental depletion for HVHS likely reflects reduced cumulative material demand per functional unit (for example, less wire loss, spatter, or consumable use due to faster deposition), which reduces upstream production of alloying and processing steps that carry trace-metal burdens. By contrast, the small increase in fossil-fuel depletion for HVHS is consistent with higher instantaneous arc power at elevated voltage: although HVHS shortens total deposition time, the larger per-second electricity draw raises the non-renewable energy consumed per wall slightly. ODP values remain trivial for both strategies and do not affect these depletion conclusions [32].

To facilitate an overarching comparison of the two WAAM scenarios, the ReCiPe 2016 endpoint method (Hierarchist perspective) was employed. This methodology aggregates the results from various impact categories into three areas of protection: damage to human health, damage to ecosystems, and resource availability. These are subsequently normalized and weighted into a single score, expressed in milli-points (mPt). This endpoint aggregation provides a consolidated metric of the total environmental burden, enabling a clear, cradle-to-gate comparison that is valuable for decision-making [33]. The underlying midpoint results remain essential, however, for diagnosing specific trade-offs between the individual environmental impacts of each process strategy. Figure 5 presents the ReCiPe 2016 (H) endpoint LCA results.

Fig. 5. LCA results of the EPD 2018 impact category

The ReCiPe endpoint aggregation gives 52 mPt for HVHS and 47 mPt for LVLS, an absolute difference of 5 mPt (HVHS is $\approx 10.6\%$ higher than LVLS when LVLS is used as the baseline). This means that, when individual impact categories are weighted and combined into damage to human health, ecosystems, and resource availability, the HVHS strategy produces a larger total damage score despite reducing several specific mid-level impacts (water scarcity, eutrophication, and elemental depletion). The reason is straightforward: small but consistent increases in energy-related midpoints for HVHS (fossil-fuel depletion, GWP, acidification, and POCP carry comparatively large weights in the endpoint calculation and therefore dominate the aggregated result; the reductions in water use and some material-related midpoints are not large enough to offset those energy-driven damages under the chosen characterization and weighting.

3. Conclusion

This study conducted an integrated experimental and LCA to evaluate the environmental performance of two WAAM deposition strategies differing in arc voltage and travel speed. The results demonstrate that environmental differences between high- and low-voltage conditions are small but non-negligible, emphasizing the critical trade-off between process speed and instantaneous energy demand.

- The GWP of the HVHS condition (0.746 kg CO₂-eq) was only 0.94% higher than LVLS (0.739 kg CO₂-eq).
- In endpoint aggregation, HVHS showed $\sim 10.6\%$ higher total impacts, due to elevated instantaneous power outweighing shorter deposition time.
- Electrical parameter tuning (voltage-speed balance) significantly affects energy efficiency and should be optimized alongside geometry control.
- Accurate, real-time measurement of energy consumption provides a more reliable LCA baseline than theoretical power estimates.

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